

DETERMINATION OF WATER IN ACETIC ACID WITH ACETIC ANHYDRIDE AND ANILINE

BY MIHIR NATH DAS

The simplest method for the determination of water in organic compounds is based on the reaction of water with acetic anhydride or acetyl chloride, followed by titration with alkali (Smith and Bryant, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 841; Toennies and Elliott, *ibid.*, p. 2136). Other similar reagents that have been used for the same purpose include benzoic anhydride (Ross, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1932, 51, 1217), aluminium chloride (Fischbeck and Eckert, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1938, 112, 305), α -naphthyl-dichlorophosphine oxide (Lindner, *ibid.*, 1925, 66, 305), α -naphthoxydichlorophosphine (Bell, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2903), cinnamoyl chloride (Van Nieuwenberg, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1937, 1, 71), etc. These acidimetric methods cannot, however, be used for the determination of small amounts of water in acetic acid or other acids. The Fischer titration (*Angew. Chem.*, 1935, 48, 394) has recently found wide acceptance for determination of water in various compounds, and numerous improvements in the technique have been devised to suit specific requirements (Mitchell, Jr. and Smith, "Aquametry", Interscience, New York, 1949). The Fischer method has been used with success to determine small quantities of water in various organic and inorganic acids. But the cost and special techniques involved tend to restrict its use only to cases where determination of water is a matter of routine procedure.

The method described herein is based on the acid-catalysed reaction between water and a known amount of acetic anhydride, dissolved in glacial acetic acid, and estimation of the excess anhydride left unchanged. So, the problem ultimately reduces to the determination of acetic anhydride in acetic acid.

Toennies and Elliott's polarimetric method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 902) for determination of acetic anhydride in glacial acetic acid depends on the measurement of the decrease in optical activity as a result of the reaction between camphoric acid and acetic anhydride, producing camphoric anhydride, the reaction being catalysed by small concentrations of strong acids. They have used this method for determination of water in acetic acid. Siggia and Hanna (*Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 1717) have determined several acid anhydrides in presence of carboxylic acids by allowing the anhydride to react with a known amount of aniline, and estimating the excess aniline by potentiometric titration in ethyleneglycol-isopropyl alcohol mixture. Benson and Kitchen (*Canadian J. Res.*, 1949, 27, 266) have determined acetic anhydride in acetic acid with aniline by estimating the excess aniline colorimetrically with furfuraldehyde. Very recently (Greathouse *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, 28, 357) the acid-catalysed reaction between water and acetic anhydride has been utilised for determination of either water or acetic anhydride in acetic acid by thermometric titration. According to the present method, the excess aniline is titrated directly with perchloric acid in

glacial acetic acid medium, using methyl violet as indicator. The acetanilide, formed by the reaction between acetic anhydride and aniline, is too weak a base even in glacial acetic acid medium, and does not interfere with the titration of free aniline.

Acetic anhydride solution (0.1-0.2M) in acetic acid containing 0.001N-HClO₄ was used. The solution was standardised with aniline as described below. The strength of the solution changed rather rapidly and was checked before use.

0.1N-Perchloric acid solution in glacial acetic acid, standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate, using methyl violet or crystal violet as indicator (Seaman and Allen, *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, 23, 591), was employed. 72% Perchloric acid may be used for preparation of the standard solution; the water introduced with the acid does not interfere.

Aniline was freshly distilled over caustic soda. A standard solution (0.1-0.2 M) of aniline in anhydrous acetic acid can be prepared as follows. To remove any moisture that may be present in "glacial" acetic acid, acetic anhydride is added (10 c.c. per litre of acid or more, if necessary) and allowed to stand overnight. Sufficient aniline is then added so that the final concentration of free aniline is 0.1-0.2 M, a part of the aniline being converted into acetanilide by reaction with free acetic anhydride. The solution was kept in a coloured glass-stoppered bottle and standardised by titration with 0.1 N-HClO₄ in acetic acid. The solution, so prepared and preserved, has been found to remain colorless and maintain constant strength for several days.

Glacial acetic acid used was distilled over anhydrous calcium sulphate. No special purification for removing traces of water is necessary. The solvent must be neutral to methyl violet (0.2% solution in glacial acetic acid).

Procedure: Standardisation of acetic anhydride solution in acetic acid.—A measured volume of the solution containing 2-3 millimoles of anhydride was treated with 3-4 millimoles of aniline in a glass-stoppered bottle or conical flask. After 5 minutes, the free aniline was titrated with 0.1 N-HClO₄ in glacial acetic acid using methyl violet as indicator. The first disappearance of violet tinge of the indicator was taken as the end-point.

Instead of using a standard solution of aniline, the base may be directly weighed out into the acetic anhydride, but the purity of aniline must be checked by titration with HClO₄ in acetic acid. The precision of the method was tested by determining acetic anhydride in acetic acid in replicates, using the same solution. The reproducibility data are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Number	...	1	2	3	4	5
Molar conc. of anhydride found		0.1068	0.1073	0.1070	0.1071	0.1074
					Average 0.1071 ± 0.0003	

Determination of water in acetic acid.—Different amounts of water were directly weighed out into a known volume of the standard solution of acetic anhydride in a glass-stoppered bottle or conical flask. The hydrolysis of acetic anhydride was strongly catalysed by HClO₄ (0.001 N) present in the solution, and the reaction was complete in less than 10 minutes. The excess of acetic anhydride was then estimated with aniline as described above. Results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Water taken.	Conc. of water in reaction mixture.	Water found.	% Error.
0.2267 g.	0.45 %	0.2259 g.	-0.35
0.1427	0.23	0.1416	-0.77
0.0918	0.46	0.0910	-0.87
0.0825	0.41	0.0827	+0.25
0.0480	0.16	0.0485	+1.04
0.0468	0.09	0.0470	+0.43

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SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF THE DISSOCIATION CONSTANT OF HYDROXYLAMINE

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The present work was undertaken in order to check independently the value of the dissociation constant of hydroxylamine, obtained conductometrically in this laboratory (this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 101). Experiments showed that in the case of hydroxylamine, the method of Stenström and Goldsmith (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1683) was the most suitable.

Hydroxylamine is known to be highly diastinctive in the aqueous solution (Hartley and Dobbie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 77, 318) as in the gas phase (Smith and Leighton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 172); it exhibits continuous absorption in the region 2015 to 2350 Å or further, depending on the length of the optical path and the concentration or pressure of hydroxylamine. This shows that unlike aniline (Flexser *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1935, 57, 2103) and pyridine (Andon *et al.*, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 910) here concentrated solutions and longer optical paths have to be used.

The apparatus consisted of a Unicam quartz spectrophotometer (model Sp. 500), a hydrogen lamp combined with a stabilised power pack and quartz cells of 4 cm optical path. A series of phosphate buffers (p_H 2 to 11) made from $M/10-H_3PO_4$ and $M/10-KOH$ were prepared and their p_H was determined on a Beckman model-G p_H -meter, previously standardised against standard buffers.

Pure hydroxylamine was prepared by the method of Hurd and Brownstein (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 67). It was dissolved in water to form a strong solution, the strength of which was determined by the bromate method. It was then diluted to $\sim M/2$; 1 c.c. of this was diluted to 25 c.c. by adding the required buffer. Tests showed that this solution had the same p_H as the original buffer. The blank contained the appropriate buffer to which 1 c.c. of distilled water was added. The absorption measurements were